

Fijuu2: A Game-Based Audio-Visual Performance and Composition Engine

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Biographical information.

Julian Oliver is a free-software developer, composer and artist based in Berlin, Germany. Julian has presented papers and artworks at major international electronic-art events and conferences worldwide alongside performances of game based electroacoustic works at prominent venues in the EU, US, Japan and the South Pacific. Julian has given numerous workshops in game-design, independent game-engine development, virtual architecture and open source development practices worldwide.

Steven Pickles is an Australian artist, programmer and free software developer currently based in Berlin, Germany. He has collaborated on numerous projects with groups such as farmersmanual, FoAM, Select Parks and meso.

Description of Piece.

Fijuu2 is the second iteration of the audio-visual project 'Fijuu' and was commissioned by the CyberSonica festival in London 2006. Fijuu2 takes ideas from this first performance-based version and brings the tool into the domain of a public installation, placing particular attention on providing the player with a set of intuitive compositional tools.

Fijuu2 features six unique 3D instruments, each of which may be 'sculpted' using Playstation2 like gamepads. The player manipulates forms and changes in the signal result. At any point the player can record a segment of desired length to a 3D track, represented as a spinning ring in the scene. Through layering recorded segments, and changing the amplitude and rotation speed of these segments, rich compositions are quickly produced.

Fijuu2 seeks to move beyond the 'visualiser plugin' approach to digital audio-visual experiments, where sound fed into a system is analysed and graphical effects result. Fijuu2 reverses this control model, seating the player at the centre of action where only through direct manipulation of scene elements can signal be produced and arranged. To help players feel comfortable using the piece, we chose an input device millions around the world are already familiar with, the Playstation2 gamepad.

Fijuu2 was enjoyed by many hundreds of visitors to CyberSonica06 in London, and proved itself as a robust and popular component of the exhibition overall. The project has since sparked interest in areas not directly related to the audio-visual arts, appearing in Computer Music Magazine, The Tate Britain and inviting interest from Sony Entertainment Europe.

Please see <http://fjuu.com/outline> for images, a floorplan and sample videos of this work in action.